

**CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF T300/914 LAMINATES
USING THE LOCAL VISCOELASTIC RESPONSE**

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ABSTRACT

The object of this research is to experimentally determine the effects of temperature and moisture content on the mechanical behaviour of resin matrix laminates. Unidirectional and cross ply T300/914 moisture saturated laminates were subjected to tensile loadings under various relative humidities (0 %, 80 %, 96 % RH and immersed in distilled water) at 60°C. Both time dependent dynamic and quasi-static in-plane responses were analyzed. The results indicate that the behaviour is not substantially altered in fibre controlled deformation process but that the viscoelastic characteristics in matrix controlled mechanisms are considerably modified.

INTRODUCTION

The paper deals with the characterization of the mechanical behaviour of unidirectional and cross ply T300/914 laminated specimens under constant rate tensile loadings and various environmental conditions. It is a part of an extensive experimental programme whose main objective is to build relevant models which could be used to compute the time and moisture dependent mechanical responses of composite structures.

Most of the commonly used procedures of structure design still assume a linear elastic behaviour up to the ultimate strength. They completely neglect the strong dependence of the failure properties on the past mechanical history. The viscoelastic properties of fibrous composites are induced by the resin matrix and in many cases significant viscoelastic effects can be detected in the fibre direction of unidirectional laminates [1, 2], so they must be taken into account. Specific effects, such as strain relaxations and stress rearrangements, which will occur with laminated structures under service conditions cannot be predicted using traditional elastic assumptions.

A consistent prediction of the failure is necessarily based upon the investigation of the major process of material deformation. The modelization of the time dependent response is absolutely necessary to estimate the long term behaviour and failure of structures submitted to given

environmental conditions. In particular it must be pointed out that internal dissipation under dynamic efforts has to be evaluated because it can modify the local strain and stress fields and initiate some damage.

The paper first focuses upon the special experimental methodology which will give informations both on the dynamic and time dependent in-plane strain responses of a single tensile sample; the technique tends to minimize the experimental scatter and can provide an interesting insight into the deformation process. The main results are then commented and the effects of the properties of the fibres and of the matrix on the composite behaviour are successively examined for various moisture conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials are unidirectional $[0]_4S$ and cross ply $[0/90]_2S$ T300/914 laminates cut from panels fabricated from prepreg at Aérospatiale (Suresnes, France). The panels were 600 mm by 300 mm by 1 mm (nominal thickness) rectangular plates. The tensile specimens, 200 mm (or 160 mm) by 13 mm, were cut from the plates using a cooled diamond cut-off wheel and their edges were carefully smoothed using fine glass paper. Fibre volume fraction was controlled to 62 ± 3 percent according to ASTM D792-66 and D31 71-76. The six tested configurations are defined by the angle θ of the fibre direction l of the outer ply with respect to the load direction x : $[0]_4S$, $[10]_4S$, $[45]_4S$, $[90]_4S$, $[0/90]_2S$, $[90/0]_2S$.

Prior to moisture absorption, all the specimens were preconditioned in an oven at 40, 60 and 90°C successively to constant weight in order to provide an initially dry condition and the cross section sizes were measured. Chamfered aluminium tabs (40 mm by 13 mm by 2 mm) were bonded to the laminate after sand blasting and anodic etching. The edges were then coated with polyurethan varnish. Four specimens of each material are exposed to 80 and 96 % relative humidity at 60°C until an equilibrium moisture content is obtained. Exposures take place on racks placed in sealed dessicators containing saturated salt solutions (KCl , K_2SO_4) whose vapor pressure when in equilibrium under atmospheric pressure gives steady values (3% RH). Some specimens are also immersed in distilled water at 60°C. Reference specimens without tabs are periodically removed and weighted to the nearest 0.1 mg on a Sartorius type 2842 balance. The conditioned specimens were tested after they reached an apparent equilibrium gain; the exposure time was about four months which was in agreement with results previously obtained by Aérospatiale [3]. The choice of the temperature 60°C had been made to activate the absorption process to get a reasonable exposure time.

All tests were carried out at 60°C on dry and saturated specimens at 80 %, 96 % RH and saturated by water immersion. They were conducted in an TEE/LN2/80 Schenk environmental chamber fixed on a servo-hydraulic 810 MTS test machine.

Each specimen was instrumented by a 0-90 rosette (Vishay cea 85-125-UT-120) and a uniaxial gauge (Vishay cea 85-125-UN-120) at 0° and 45° to the longitudinal axis respectively; the two gauges were symmetrically bonded on the same face with respect to its transverse axis and were temperature and humidity compensated using dummy gauges on an unstressed specimen cut from the same laminate. The sizes of the gauge grids had been chosen in order to get average strain values along the specimen width. The

transverse-sensitivity effects of the strain gauges have been corrected and the eventual misalignment angles have been checked systematically. It is worth to emphasize that the use of three strain gauges allowed us to estimate the whole state of strain of the surface. That is quite fundamental when dealing with an **anisotropic** material.

During the test the specimen was subjected to a uniaxial stress σ_x such that :

$$\sigma_x = \dot{\sigma}_0 t + a \sin(\omega t) f(t)$$

$f(t)$ switching periodically between 0 and 1 and a being the **small** amplitude of the sinusoidal stress. The stresses were estimated with reference to the initial cross section of the dry specimen as no appreciable changes of it could be detected during the absorption process or during the test. The main test parameters are defined on figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Stress versus time

The three strain gauges were wired to a 2100 Vishay multichannel conditioner. The outputs were multiplexed through a 50M40 Tektronix programmable relay scanner to a 1250 Enertec frequency analyzer, which was continuously supplied with the dynamic load signal. The analyser provided in real time the two characteristics of the complex strain to load ratios. A DEC Rainbow 100 was used as a GPIB controller and data-logging system (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Schematic of the test system.

The constant rate of loading $\dot{\sigma}_0$ was adjusted to obtain a time to failure of about 1000 s, so it can vary with the different types of specimens. Usual constant rate tensile tests without any superimposed sinusoidal stress have been first performed to determine the convenient test rate and check that no perturbation was induced by the additional dynamic stress. The duration of each dynamic stage was about 1 % of the expected life time to limit the alteration of the quasi-static response to the ramp. Allowing 3 cycles for the mechanical system to settle, and 30 cycles per measurement to ensure an accuracy of ± 0.5 % on the moduli, 93 (rounded to 100) cycles were required. As a consequence a suitable value of the frequency was 10 Hz. The starting time of the first harmonic test depends on the specimen, it is fixed such that the amplitude of the dynamic stress is less than 20 % of the ramp stress at that time.

The test could thus provide the time dependent quasi-static in-plane response to the ramp and the dynamic plane response at different times during the test. The harmonic analysis of the response of some specimens revealed that the influence of the harmonics are quite negligible, so the dynamic response could be studied within the framework of **linear viscoelasticity**. Consequently the analysis of the dynamic stress and strains immediately leads to the experimental estimates of the dynamic moduli and phases of the local **complex compliances** S_{xxxx}^* , S_{yyxx}^* and S_{xyxx} in tensorial notations (x and y being the longitudinal and transverse specimen axis respectively). These compliances are components of the fourth order compliance tensor which characterizes the local dynamic behaviour of the material at the time of the analysis. Then specific dynamic responses, such as shear response for instance, can be easily deduced from this set of experimental compliances. At last this local dynamic response is obviously dependent upon the history of the deformation; it could be eventually considered as function of the relaxed equilibrium state when the rate of deformation is low.

The quasi-static response is generally characterized by a non-linear variation of the in-plane strain versus time curve ; such a non-linear response does not imply that the behaviour is non-linear and gives no information a priori about the deformation process. Nevertheless the comparison of the **tangent compliances**, defined as the tangents to the strain-stress curves, and the dynamic response can provide straightforward informations about the time dependent properties and can be used to check viscoelastic models in particular. It must be kept in mind that those tangent compliances are **not** the components of a tensor and that all basis transformations only hold for the strains and stresses.

RESULTS AND COMMENTS

In the following, for sake of simplicity (a star refers to the complex quantities):

$d\sigma_x/d\epsilon_x$	will be referred to as 'tangent longitudinal modulus',
$ \sigma_x^*/\epsilon_x^* $	as 'dynamic longitudinal modulus',
$d\sigma_x/d\epsilon_y$	as 'tangent cross modulus',
$ \sigma_x^*/\epsilon_y^* $	as 'dynamic cross modulus',

Figure 3. Longitudinal modulus of $[0]_{4S}$ (D dynamic, T tangent)

Figure 4. Longitudinal modulus of $[90/0]_{2S}$ (D dynamic, T tangent)

$d\tau/d\gamma$ as 'tangent shear modulus',
 $|G^*|$ as 'dynamic shear modulus'.

Evolution of the dynamic moduli along the tests will show non-linearity of the specimen behaviour, whereas distinct evolutions of the tangent and dynamic moduli will show its dependence upon the history of loading, i.e. the appearance of delayed strains.

The mechanical response of the material used will depend on the interactions between the fibre properties, the matrix properties and the structural effects.

Fibre Controlled Behaviour:

The dynamic longitudinal modulus of the unidirectional $[0]_{4S}$ (fig.3) increases along the test (+15% for 1.2% strain) showing a non-linear hardening of the carbon fibres, already mentioned in a number of papers [4,5], although we find a rate of increase grossly half smaller.

The tangent longitudinal modulus approximatively follows the dynamic one, thus indicating a purely **elastic** behaviour of the fibres. A minor influence of humidity results in a lesser increase of the tangent modulus as moisture content increases.

That non-linear elastic response of the fibres determines the dynamic longitudinal modulus of the $[90/0]_{2S}$ and $[0/90]_{2S}$ laminates, which is half the value of the $[0]_{4S}$'s one (fig. 4). The tangent longitudinal modulus first increases like the dynamic one to about 0.4 % and then stabilizes. Those apparent delayed strains could be induced by the microcracking of the transverse plies which occurs in this strain region.

Matrix Controlled Behaviour:

A variety of results showed the occurrence of a delayed response of the matrix. We will emphasize here upon its **shear properties**. The dynamic and tangent shear modulus have been derived from the 10° and 45° off axis test data. Results are shown on figures 5 and 6.

Dynamic response: there is a marked variation of the dynamic shear modulus along the test: up to 15% decrease at failure. So, the epoxy resin has also a non-linear behaviour. Moreover, the evolution of the shear loss angle shows a noticeable increase of the internal damping (fig. 6).

Figure 6. Shear loss angle evolution for $[10]_{4S}$.

Figure 5. Shear modulus evolution from tensile tests on $[10]_{4S}$ and $[45]_{4S}$ (D dynamic, T tangent).

The dynamic response is very sensitive to environmental conditions: about -20% on the modulus and -0.5% on the shear loss angle when hygrometry varies from 0% RH to 96% RH. Such a result is consistent with a softening of the matrix with moisture.

Tangent response: The curves on figure 5 clearly show that visco-elasticity is probably the main feature of the resin behaviour and cannot be discarded even in rough approximation. Indeed, the relaxation phenomena within the resin can lower its tangent shear modulus almost to zero. Hence, resin appears here as a fluid rather than as a solid.

The evolution of this modulus is well depicted by an exponential law:

$$G = G_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0}\right) \quad (1)$$

as can be seen on figure 7 where G has been logarithmically plotted. Values of G_0 and γ_0 are given in table 1. Emphasis is made upon the fact that eq. (1) is not a law of behaviour, i.e. a biunivoqual relation between G and γ , but the response of the material under its particular history of loading.

Figure 7. Logarithmic plot of G vs γ for $[10]_{4S}$ (X) and $[45]_{4S}$ (Δ).

θ	10 deg	45 deg
Dry	$G_0 = 7.24$ GPa $\epsilon_0 = 0.88$ %	$G_0 = 6.35$ GPa $\epsilon_0 = 0.77$ %
96% RH	$G_0 = 5.10$ GPa $\epsilon_0 = 0.75$ %	$G_0 = 3.42$ GPa $\epsilon_0 = 0.68$ %

Table 1. Tangent shear modulus characteristics.

Here too, the influence of moisture content is of major importance, either on the initial value G_0 of G or on the rate of decrease governed by γ_0 .

The curves on figure 7 are roughly parallel to each other, but the

initial value of G depends strongly on the angle θ . This could be a consequence of end constraint effects induced by fixed grips during off axis tests, which lead to overestimated values of the shear modulus. Following [6], results for $\theta = 45^\circ$ can be held as reasonable estimates of the true values. Further analysis taking into account those end constraint effects has been undertaken.

Those viscoelastic properties allow us to understand the increase of more than 100% of the tangent cross modulus of the cross-ply laminates (fig. 8). Whereas their fibre-dominated longitudinal behaviour is elastic, there is a relaxation of the transverse strain, and thus apparent stiffening as the longitudinal stress remains the same. The dependence of this effect on moisture content is not clear and maybe disappears within experimental scatter.

As a conclusion, the present results show that trying to measure 'the' shear modulus of a composite lamina is something like aiming at a moving target. Relaxation phenomena within the resin are of the utmost importance and may lead to fluid-like long term behaviour. Moreover, one cannot underestimate the effect of moisture, responsible for variations of the shear modulus within tens of percents. Hence, an actual **shear modulus** depends upon the **whole hygrothermal and mechanical history**.

Structure Effects:

This paragraph does not concern the behaviour of the material, but the effects of the laminate stacking sequence upon strain gauge measurements made on the surface of the test samples.

In particular, the outer ply orientation (90 or 0 deg) has a significant influence on the results of transverse strain measurements. For a given plate strain state, the strain measured by the transverse gauge is lesser for the $[90/0]_{2S}$ than for the $[0/90]_{2S}$ laminate, this leading to an apparent stiffer cross modulus for the first laminate: 1.4 versus 1.2 TPa (fig 8).

Figure 8. Cross modulus evolution for $[0/90]_{2S}$ (I) and $[90/0]_{2S}$ (II) (D: dynamic; T: tangent).

This relation between the longitudinal and the transverse strains measured on the surface, if non linear, could be responsible for the increase of the dynamic cross modulus of those laminates: +30% at failure (fig 8).

CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this work has been to characterize trends of the **in-plane mechanical response** under **different relative humidities at 60 C.** The dynamic and quasi-static responses are both functions of hygrothermal conditions and mechanical history and it appeared that moisture dependent viscoelastic response must be taken into account in tests designed to assess the mechanical response of graphite epoxy laminates. In particular the **shear properties**, which are of primary importance in structure design, are substantially dependent upon the environmental conditions because of the resin viscoelastic properties. Improved moisture and time dependent models are required to predict the material response under service conditions.

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